

A Global Biodata Coalition White Paper

Working Cooperatively for Global Biodata Resource Sustainability

Executive Summary

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Biodata resources are essential to the global research endeavour in the life sciences and biomedicine, but the current funding for these resources is fragmented, uncoordinated and far from secure. Sustaining the global biodata infrastructure is a critical and growing challenge that requires urgent and cooperative action.

The Global Biodata Coalition (GBC) developed this White Paper as a step to meet this challenge. It identifies the key areas where research funders need to work with biodata resources and wider stakeholder communities to build solutions. It provides a framework through which GBC and its member funders will work to advance these goals.

The White Paper calls for the adoption of nine foundational principles as the framework for cooperative funding models to enhance sustainability of the global biodata infrastructure as listed on the next page.

Cooperative funding to sustain the global biodata infrastructure: Nine Foundational Principles

1. Those who fund life science research share responsibility for ensuring that data resources are sustained.
2. Life science research funders of all types should contribute to biodata resource sustainability.
3. Funders should contribute through means that are appropriate to their situation.
4. Sustainability will be required both for existing resources and for new resources that are established to respond to new data types and technologies.
5. Funding approaches should not require payment at the point of use of a biodata resource unless this is the only viable option. Where payments are required, they should be equitable and fair, and should not restrict access to data based on ability to pay.
6. Models for sustainability must allow for the participation of funders whose funds cannot move across national borders.
7. Biodata resources should develop governance structures that support the interests of funding organisations and the institutions that host biodata resources.
8. Biodata resources should ensure data and metadata are as open as possible and as closed as necessary—balancing the need to reduce friction and costs to access for users whilst providing proportionate governance and safeguards where required.
9. All biodata resources should have a clear strategy for sustainability, including appropriate succession plans.

Building on these Principles, the White Paper then makes detailed recommendations for:

- Developing, testing and implementing new and innovative cooperative funding mechanisms
- Coordinating support for research funders to sustain the global biodata resource infrastructure

GBC will work with research funders, biodata resource managers and other stakeholders to implement this White Paper.

GBC will use this White Paper to stimulate discussion and debate among these groups and use the outputs on an ongoing basis to shape our approach and drive activities at national, regional and global levels to address this critical challenge.

Global Biodata Coalition

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